

Creating a Custom distributed runtime activity anomaly detection framework to enable SIEMLESS advanced detection capabilities: A Literature Review

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Abstract — this article introduces the reader to ways of creating a framework that detects anomalies through logs without the need to use SIEM for advanced detection capabilities. Due to the increase of the cyber-attacks and their complications it is necessary to think of the way to oversee each single of the threat in real time. This paper will help to understand the basics of the log monitoring frameworks that were developed before and cover the main problems and complications along the way of developing such framework depending on the variety of way to train the algorithm for future detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays cyberattacks had become a serious threat due to constant complications black hats might create, which is causing a lot of trouble to everyone, not only users, but specifically targets companies, CEOs, or any other founders. It had been stated by Ghafir I. et al (2018), that in 2015 the cost of cyberattacks was \$3 trillion and increased even more since 2021 [10]. Such numbers and statistics made people especially concerned about safety, starting to look for methods to prevent any malicious intended actions. Unlike other methods, like firewall or antivirus, log monitoring has a lot of benefits that those applications and ways to protect

don't. According to Ghafir I. et al (2018), "Although virus scanners, firewalls and intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDPSs) have been able to detect and prevent many of cyber attacks, cyber-criminals in turn have developed more advanced methods and techniques to intrude into the target's network and exploit their resources, targeting both wired and wireless communications" (p. 2) [10]. Even though the technologies are more advanced now, the hackers with malicious intent are developing, too, always finding more complicated ways to find some information, some ways to intrude. This is why people were researching on ways to improve log monitoring system to spot and alarm the users about anomaly that it detected. By this year, starting from 2015, a lot of articles about log monitoring and anomaly detecting framework were published. During these 10 year researchers have published over **214 thousands of articles regarding this topic**, and lower, in Figure 1, you can analyze how the relevance of the topic increased in a few years. This increase shows importance of the research regarding topic of log monitoring – a lot of people are agreeing on the need of developing frameworks, confident that such developments would set us, cybersecurity specialists, ahead, allowing

to detect the malicious intent in a quick way.

NUMBER OF ARTICLES PUBLISHED

Figure 1

Since 2015 the number of articles written for this topic had increased by 6 times, showing the relevance and importance of it, probably, due to increase of machine learning, deep learning and AI usage. The most cited article regarding the topic of log monitoring framework had 2 thousands of citations, and it was about their framework named DeepLog created by using deep learning method. It shows one of the variety of the ways to implement deep learning, but there are plenty of works related to unsupervised vision and supervised. By this time, it's still unclear what would be the best way to develop such an algorithm for malicious activity, but it is our goal to determine which one is more profitable to use. It is our main goal to find out which way of learning can contribute better to threat detection and why.

II. METHODOLOGY

This article will be based on Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework to identify the best possible articles regarding the topic we will cover, presenting the transparency of our choices to make sure this literature review paper has the most fitting articles

for the review. PRISMA is a framework needed to ensure transparent filtering of the articles the researcher had found, just so the reader won't be concerned about biased choice of the articles.

It consists of a few steps: Topic selection, Database Search, Keyword definition, Identification of studies, screening, eligibility assessment, inclusion.

Regarding the topic "Creating a Custom distributed runtime activity anomaly detection framework to enable SIEMLESS advanced detection capabilities" there were plenty of resources to choose from, but ensuring choice of the best articles, I've listed the most important keywords regarding the topic I am covering: **log monitoring, log parsing, machine learning, unsupervised learning, supervised learning, threat hunting, anomaly detection, Sysmon, deep learning.**

Those are the keywords I will be working with to ensure the best results while conducting the research. For this research and literature reviews I've been using only one database – Google Scholar to make sure I won't be getting a lot of duplicates while searching and filtering. While conducting the search process, I've found 18000 articles that are the most relevant to my topic. In figure 2 you can see how I've been filtering the articles

I've got in Google Scholar:

Figure 2. PRISMA framework

After finding the articles that were the most relevant for me, acknowledging the first step of PRISMA framework, which is identification, I ensured none of them were duplicating, but since I had only one database I was working with, I knew none of the publications would appear more than once. I would've excluded some if I were working with a few databases, but since I didn't there was a guarantee publications weren't duplicated. After seeing 18000 articles, I have excluded more than 17880 just

because for my conducted research I needed only most relevant ones that appeared on the first pages of the Google Scholar, so excluding 17880 articles, I was left with 120 articles that I needed to evaluate further. The next step of PRISMA framework is excluding the articles that the researcher couldn't get access to, but when conducting the first screening step I had found that a few of the articles were accessible only with purchase, so it leads to me excluding 10 of found articles. The last step of screening part was excluding a few more articles to ensure getting more relevant ones to analyze and cite during the literature review. During this step I have excluded 64 articles: 34 weren't relevant enough to be included, 15 weren't cited by anyone, 19 were focused on SIEM-based solutions, but since my thesis is focused on finding solution without SIEM, I found those unnecessary to include. Therefore, I was left with 42 articles I needed to read, analyze only those out of all possible ones, since regarding PRISMA those were the only ones that were the most relevant for my literature review. In Table 1 you can see all the articles, I've found relevant for my topic of research, sorted by the citation number.

Table 1. All articles retrieved after PRISMA framework.

1.	Du M. et al, 2017	Deeplog: Anomaly detection and diagnosis from system logs through deep learning	Acm.org	Anomaly detection; deep learning; log data analysis.	2164
2.	Agrawal S. & Agrawal J., 2015	Survey on anomaly detection using data mining techniques	Sciencedirect.com	Anomaly Detection Clustering Classification Data Mining Intrusion Detection System.	881
3.	Nassif A. et al, 2021	Machine learning for anomaly detection: A systematic review	IEEE	Anomaly detection, machine learning, security and privacy protection.	813
4.	He S. et al, 2016	Experience report: System log analysis for anomaly detection	IEEE	Anomaly detection; Sysmon; Log analysis; threat hunting	788

5.	Zhang X. et al, 2019	Robust log-based anomaly detection on unstable log data	Aiops.org	Anomaly Detection, Log Analysis, Deep Learning, Log Instability, Data Quality	780
6.	Habeeb R. et al, 2019	Real-time big data processing for anomaly detection: A survey	Core.ac.uk	Real-time, big data processing, anomaly detection and machine learning algorithms.	665
7.	Ghafir I. et al, 2018	Detection of advanced persistent threat using machine-learning correlation analysis	ScienceDirect.com	Cyber attacks, advanced persistent threat, malware, intrusion detection system, alert correlation, machine learning	366
8.	Le V.; Zhang H., 2021	Log-based anomaly detection without log parsing	IEEE	Anomaly Detection, Log Analysis, Log Parsing, Deep Learning	316
9.	Le V.; Zhang H., 2022	Log-based anomaly detection with deep learning: How far are we?	IEEE	Anomaly Detection, Log Analysis, Log Parsing, Deep Learning	257
10.	Yang L. et al, 2021	Semi-supervised log-based anomaly detection via probabilistic label estimation.	IEEE	Log Analysis, Anomaly Detection, Deep Learning, Probabilistic Estimation, Label	254
11.	Rehman ur MH. et al, 2016	Big data reduction methods: a survey	Springer.com	Big data Data compression Data reduction Data complexity Dimensionality reduction	246
12.	Lee J. et al, 2019	Cyber threat detection based on artificial neural networks using event profiles	IEEE	Cyber security, intrusion detection, network security, artificial intelligence, deep neural networks.	227
13.	Shaukat K. et al, 2020	Cyber threat detection using machine learning techniques: A performance evaluation perspective	IEEE	Cyber Threat; Cybercrime; Performance Evaluation; Machine Learning Application; Intrusion Detection System; Malware Detection; Spam Classification	217
14.	Landauer M. et al, 2024	A critical review of common log data sets used for evaluation of sequence-based anomaly detection techniques	Acm.org	Log data Anomaly detection Neural networks Deep learning	193
15.	Chen Z. et al, 2021	Experience report: Deep learning-based system log analysis for anomaly detection	Arxiv.org	Log analysis, anomaly detection, deep learning	169
16.	Manoharan A.; Sarker M., 2023	Revolutionizing cybersecurity: Unleashing the power of artificial intelligence and machine learning for next-generation threat detection	Academia.edu	Analysis, Cybersecurity, Artificial intelligence, Machine Learning, threat detection, anomaly detection	161
17.	Mohammed A., 2023	SOC Audits in Action: Best Practices for Strengthening Threat Detection and Ensuring Compliance	Academia.edu	SOC audits, cybersecurity, compliance, threat detection, key metrics, audit methodologies, control effectiveness.	158
18.	Farzad A.; Gulliver T., 2020	Unsupervised log message anomaly detection	Sciencedirect.com	Anomaly detection Classification Deep learning Log messages Unsupervised learning	145
19.	Debnath B. et al, 2018	LogLens: A real-time log analysis system	IEEE	Log analysis, anomaly detection, machine learning, log parsing	140

20.	Vinayakumar R. et al, 2017	Long short-term memory based operation log anomaly detection	IEEE	Anomaly detection, Operation logs, deep learning: Recurrent neural network (RNN), Long short-term memory (LSTM) and Stacked-long short-term memory (S-LSTM)	134
21.	Chukwunweike J. et al, 2024	Harnessing Machine Learning for Cybersecurity: How Convolutional Neural Networks are Revolutionizing Threat Detection and Data Privacy	Researchgate.net	Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Cybersecurity, Anomaly Detection, Machine Learning, Threat Detection, Data Privacy	125
22.	Ma S. et al, 2015	Accurate, low cost and instrumentation-free security audit logging for windows	Chungkim.io	Logging, windows	118
23.	Chen R. et al, 2020	Logtransfer: Cross-system log anomaly detection for software systems with transfer learning	IEEE	Log Anomaly, Feature Extraction, Deep Learning, Recurrent Neural Network, Log burst.	111
24.	Yuan Y. et al, 2020	Ada: Adaptive deep log anomaly detector	IEEE	Anomaly detection, deep neural networks, logs, online training, unsupervised, log-normal, threshold	62
25.	Ongun T, et al, 2021	Living-off-the-land command detection using active learning.	Acm.org	Threat detection; Advanced Persistent Threats; Active learning for security; Contextual text embeddings	58
26.	Sindirramuti S.R., 2023	Autonomous threat hunting: A future paradigm for AI-driven threat intelligence	arXiv	Threat intelligent, Artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, autonomous treat intelligent, threat hunting.	53
27.	Ryciak P. et al, 2022	Anomaly detection in log files using selected natural language processing methods	Mdpi.com	Log analysis, natural language processing, anomaly detection, malware, word embedding	51
28.	Vaddadi SA. et al, 2023	Utilizing AI and machine learning in cybersecurity for sustainable development through enhanced threat detection and mitigation	Researchgate.net	Artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), cybersecurity within the context of fostering sustainable development	49
29.	Yu B. et al, 2024	Deep learning or classical machine learning? An empirical study on log-based anomaly detection	IEEE	Log analysis, anomaly detection, dataset, empirical study	44
30.	Landauer M. et al, 2024	A critical review of common log data sets used for evaluation of sequence-based anomaly detection techniques	Acm.org	log data analysis, anomaly detection, data sets	44
31.	Wu X. et al, 2023	On the effectiveness of log representation for log-based anomaly detection	Arxiv.org	Log representation · Anomaly detection · Automated log analysis.	31
32.	Fu Y. et al, 2023	An empirical study of the impact of log parsers on the performance of log-based anomaly detection	Github.io	Log parser · Anomaly detection · Empirical study	29
33.	Katiyar N. et al, 2024	AI and Cyber-Security: Enhancing threat detection and response with machine learning.	Academia.edu	artificial intelligence; machine learning; cyber security; intrusion detection; malware detection; anomaly detection; cyber threats	28

34.	Lv D. et al, 2021	ConAnomaly: Content-based anomaly detection for system logs.	Mdpi.com	Log anomaly detection, log sequence encoder, LSTM	28
35.	Ismail W., 2024	Threat detection and response using AI and NLP in cybersecurity	Jisis.org	Cybersecurity, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Natural Language Processing (NLP), Behavioral Analysis, Anomaly Detection.	27
36.	Khan Z. et al, 2024	Impact of log parsing on deep learning-based anomaly detection	Springer.com	Logs · Log parsing · Template identification · Anomaly detection	20
37.	Mangagondi L., 2021	Anomaly detection in log files using machine learning techniques	Diva-portal.org	Anomaly Detection, Log Files, Machine Learning, Clustering, Outlier Detection.	8
38.	Anttila T., 2020	Developing a log file analysis tool: A machine learning approach for anomaly detection	oulurepo.oulu.fi	Log file analysis, Linux log files, anomaly detection, machine learning, unsupervised learning, log parsing, design science research	3
39.	Dolak R. et al, 2018	Process Mining of Events Log from Windows	Ceur-ws.org	process mining, events log, operating system, windows	3
40.	Jasra S. et al, 2025	A Comparative Study of Unsupervised Deep Learning Methods for Anomaly Detection in Flight Data	Mdpi.com	Anomaly detection, unsupervised deep learning	2
41.	Ispaphany J. et al, 2025	A Sysmon Incremental Learning System for Ransomware Analysis and Detection.	Arxiv.com	ransomware detection machine learning incremental learning online learning concept drift detection sysmon	1
42.	Kavadias N., 2024	Understanding Living-off-the-Land Techniques, Threats, Countermeasures and Emerging Solutions.	Kavadias.net	Living of the Land (LOTL), Fileless malware, Advanced Persistent Threat (APT), Hacking, Cybersecurity	1

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The goal of our research is simple – to read, analyze and understand specific combination of methodical ideas to apply to the framework we were willing to develop. One of the main concerns is what tools to choose, what tools we should not use and back it up with detailed explanation on why we shouldn't do, why we don't find it sufficient in the long run.

The main idea of the research is creation of framework that could detect anomalies without usage of the common tool to analyze system logs – SIEM. The goal is to find a way to implement such ways to make the framework work even more sufficient when compared to existing tools and back it up with the explanation and reasoning behind the framework that

could, in our opinion, work faster and more precisely than any others. To start with the main objective, firstly, what is anomaly in cybersecurity?

Stated by Min Du et.al [1], anomaly detection is an important step in ensuring the safety within cybersecurity field.

They have stated that logging is one of the main tools to monitor the system, since system stores all events in the log event manager, for example, the system's event logs includes popular aftermarket logging utilities with **Sysmon** being the most popular one for Windows users. Through retrieving the logs specialists can check manually the errors to fix and pay attention to.

Even though reading logs to pinpoint the anomalies or system problems is easier from the point of the information being

trustworthy and precise due to the real professional checking it, it is not really beneficial and time saving lately. In opposite, it is really time consuming. Shilin He et. al [4] have explained why we can't no longer check for anomalies manually, and for that explanation cybersecurity society has more than one reason to address:

Firstly, there are too much of processes happening at the same time. The parallel nature of the modern systems makes it harder for humans to access, read and analyze each single of the logs, just because the system's behaviour started to be too complex for manual examinations.

Secondly, new devices and systems are generating too many logs, just because the system are getting not just more evolved, but more complicated, too. That's why it would be nearly impossible for one person to go through all possible logs.

Thirdly, even if person tries to pinpoint some event by using keywords, the chance of getting false positive is too high, just because the person will get logs and events that could not even in theory be close to the real failure or risk, reducing efficiency of the worker and slowing down the time given to alleviate the risks and any rising concerns.

For these reasons there is no way for us, as cybersecurity specialists, get high precision and time efficiency. At some point, due to the development of technologies, tasks that were done manually before should be completed with frameworks created to navigate the issue of human resources or problem of humans to catch up with the technologies that are developing too fast.

This is the reason why right now community of cybersecurity specialists

are creating anomaly detection frameworks by implementing different machine learning model, log parsers. Such detector could and will make the job easier by alarming the user of the suspicious activity that was never seen before. It is not a malware detector, which is why it is not oriented towards pinpointing malicious intents [2], it is a framework to see unusual for the user activity and warn the administrator or the user themselves.

By this period of time a lot of developers had created such algorithms, mostly using unsupervised machine learning type or deep learning models.

Each single one of them follows the pipeline of the development that was noticed by Shikha Agrawal and Jitendra Agrawal [2] who had noticed a pattern: *Firstly*, developers are on the stage of the **parameterization** which is a stage where they decide how they will preprocess given logs. What formats they will process it into, what is most efficient way and how the framework will run according to it.

Secondly, after first step comes **training process** – the process when developers decide if they like the precision, results or the flow of the “thinking” process of the framework.

Thirdly, after first two processes comes **detection**. Developers analyze the final product to see if they find the anomaly detection process satisfying enough. All of the developers had used Machine Learning for such goal and even though they had gotten quite satisfying results, should we trust the efficiency of the working frameworks?

Machine Learning itself can be divided on two categories: **supervised** and **unsupervised**. Supervised is a group of

algorithms that will be trained and tested only on datasets that has been labeled. Even though they show high efficiency and precision, it had been said [4] that such models will require constant labeling which is another disadvantage if we are striving to automize the detection as the process fully. Unlike supervised, unsupervised **does not** require the labeling of the dataset, which makes it easier, but in the long run it still will be needing accurate dataset. With the fact of fast development of the devices, attacking techniques those datasets used on training will sooner or later lose their meaning.

No matter how revolutionary such frameworks may seem there are a lot of factors to acknowledge and big data amount is one of them. Our systems generate many of logs daily and to create a framework to analyze all of them in real time sounds less realistic, especially given the fact that it is trained on the datasets that could not carry the latest information [6]. Not only it does not sound convincing, it is hard to send all the data to the center for it to be analyzed. It is not cost efficient for low budget companies, which is also should be acknowledged when creating the tool. Adding to the cost difficulties, there are infrastructure problems to consider. A small (or overloaded) network might not be able to support all the network traffic to forward all the logs to a central server. As much as the given solutions that exist nowadays sound promising, it could not be time saving and affordable for everyone.

Our proposal would be usage of **Powershell** and **Sysmon** – two applications that every person might have installed on their devices. Unlike ML

frameworks, it won't be trained on datasets that has generalized logs and events. We are proposing an idea to create a tool that will be analyzing your own logging "history", giving you warnings and alarms whenever it detects something unusual specifically for you, based on the logs it has collected. That way there is no need for searching for the datasets (since they play crucial role in the precision and results [4, 5]), no need for training the model. It will not only be time saving, but also carry higher precision due to personalized analysis that will be done. There won't be any need to manually update datasets to "prepare" ML frameworks for new information, it will be done more easily. We plan on implementing a way for the logs and events to be updated and added to the "system" of the framework automatically, this way we could give users the choice of how they would love to use the tool – to send all the data to the centralized server, to store and analyze it locally periodically, to analyze all local devices within one company. The tool could be versatile depending on the budget and plans to use it within a company.

IV. DISCUSSION

Based on the Literature review that we have conducted, both unsupervised and supervised are not the best solutions for the developing of the framework to detect anomalies, since there is a lot of disadvantages, starting from the inconvenience of searching and using datasets (that might make results not that accurate and give false positive), ending with the inconvenience of the data size that could slow down the process and

oppose the idea of fast framework that works in real time.

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